

METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF READING POEMS ON THE TOPIC OF THE MOTHERLAND IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. *In this article, thoughts are given on the subject of conscious, expressive, accurate, fast teaching of texts and poems in primary classes. In elementary education, it is necessary to explain to the students the need to read consciously when explaining the topics, it is necessary to be able to consciously think about what the poet wants to say when reading the material, whether it is a fragment of an artistic work or a poem. It was said that improving primary school students' conscious, fast, expressive and correct reading skills is one of the important tasks of primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *reading skills, conscious reading, expressive reading, rapid reading, accurate reading, preschool education, elementary education, text, poetry r, word meaning, dictionary.*

МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ ЧТЕНИЯ СТИХОВ НА ТЕМУ О РОДИНЕ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ

Аннотация. *В данной статье приводятся мысли на предмет осознанного, выразительного, точного, быстрого обучения текстам и стихотворениям в начальных классах. В начальном обучении необходимо объяснять учащимся необходимость осознанного чтения при объяснении темы, необходимо уметь осознанно думать о том, что хочет сказать поэт при чтении материала, является ли он фрагментом художественное произведение или стихотворение. было сказано, что совершенствование навыков осознанного, быстрого, выразительного и правильного чтения у учащихся начальных классов является одной из важных задач учителей начальных классов.*

Ключевые слова: *навыки чтения, осознанное чтение, выразительное чтение, быстрое чтение, точное чтение, дошкольное образование, начальное образование, текст, поэзия, значение слова, словарь.*

Improving primary education is considered one of the urgent tasks of today. It is known that the general human and moral skills of students, as well as initial literacy skills, are formed through primary education subjects. The educational process develops the child's potential for logical thinking, intellectual development, worldview, self-awareness, physical health, national traditions, and the wealth of our country. Today teaches to preserve, to have a conscious attitude towards nature.

From the first day a student comes to school, he should be interested in reading, read literately, and be taught to perform the first actions correctly. Reading is important in human life. A person who does not know how to read is no different from a blind person. Reading activities are carried out in primary grades in all subjects, but teaching to read is the main task of reading classes. When teaching young students to read, it is necessary to take into account their general development and psychology.

Bringing advanced pedagogical technologies to education and achieving high efficiency using the most modern, improved teaching methods is one of the urgent tasks of today. Reading lessons of primary grades have a special place in the education system according to their essence, purpose and tasks. After all, the foundations of literacy and moral education are based

on it. That is why the education of other subjects cannot be imagined without the education of reading. The student first faces the task of reading the text correctly, quickly, understanding it, and mastering its content in the reading classes. The main part of the important tasks in the education of primary school students is carried out in reading classes.

The purpose of primary school reading lessons, especially first grade reading lessons, is to develop students' conscious, fluent, expressive, and fast reading skills. Reading lessons play a very important role in solid reading of the knowledge given in the subjects of nature, etiquette, and mathematics, because the child can understand the content of the text well only if he reads correctly and fluently. There are four main components of a reading lesson that are closely related to each other.

They are: expressive reading, conscious, correct and fast reading. Three types of study are used in primary education:

1. Reading aloud
2. Reading inside
3. Whisper reading

Psychological research shows that students who are just learning to read also pay attention to the auditory sense in order to understand the text being read. Included in the section "My motherland - my golden cradle" in the 2nd grade "Reading book", "My Uzbekistan" (H. Imonberdiyev), "Istiqlal" (J. Jabborov), Country "(E. Vahidov) , "Go to the mountains" (U. Nasir). "Poem about the Motherland" (A. Avloni), "Uzbekim" (E. Vahidov) in the section "Mother is one, Motherland is one" in the 3rd grade. The country is honorable" (Kh. Davron), "Know that the country is waiting for you" (T. Malik). In the 4th grade, "Serkuyosh country" (Z. Diyar), "Iqbal buyuksan" (A. Oripov), "Tashkentnoma" (M. Shaikhzoda), "Khotira" (N. The example of such works as Norqabil is subjected to detailed analysis.

The socio-historical text's topics give a certain idea about the past of our country, the life of our people, heroic struggle, deeds of great figures, historical dates. Among them are texts about Beruni, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Babur and other ancestors. This type of works not only introduces the students to our past, but also helps them to deeply understand their filial duty and responsibility towards the Motherland.

1. Good reading qualities in students: formation of correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading.

2. To teach students to use the book, to get the necessary knowledge from it, to instill a love for the book; raising them from ordinary readers to the level of thoughtful, creative readers.

3. Expanding and enriching students' knowledge about the environment and forming their scientific outlook.

4. Educating students to be morally, aesthetically mature and in the spirit of love for work.

5. Cultivating students' connected speech and literary-aesthetic thinking.

6. Enriching students' outlook.

7. Formation of elementary literary ideas. The effectiveness of reading classes largely depends on the correct selection of educational methods.

Therefore, teaching methods, like the science itself, are in constant development. For example, in old schools, reading was taught on the basis of rote memorization, but now it is conducted on the basis of explanatory reading. In the method of memorization, no attention is

paid to commenting on the words in the text, explaining their meaning, retelling what has been read, and in general, the conscious reading.

They include more correct pronunciation, reading with recitation, expressive reading. Students' reading skills are formed and improved in reading lessons. In short, the higher the children's reading skills, the higher their mental abilities and potential. Only if we can raise our children to be conscious thinkers, we will raise a generation that is loyal to the Motherland and has a high level of thinking ability in the future.

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